

A NEW FORM OF GENERALIZED m -PF IDEALS IN BCK/BCI -ALGEBRAS

ANAS AL-MASARWAH * AND ABD GHAFUR AHMAD

ABSTRACT. In this paper, we introduce a new kind of an m -polar fuzzy ideal of a BCK/BCI -algebra called, an m -polar $(\bar{\epsilon}, \bar{\epsilon} \vee \bar{q})$ fuzzy ideal and investigate some of its properties. Ordinary ideals and m -polar $(\bar{\epsilon}, \bar{\epsilon} \vee \bar{q})$ fuzzy ideals are connected by means of level cut subset.

1. INTRODUCTION

BCK -algebras entered into mathematics in 1966 through the work of Imai and Iséki [12], and they have been applied to several domains of mathematics, such as group theory, topology, functional analysis and probability theory. Additionally, Iséki [13] initiated the idea of a BCI -algebra, which is a generalization of a BCK -algebra.

The idea of fuzzy sets was introduced by Zadeh [20] in 1965 to handle uncertainties in several real applications, and the idea of bipolar fuzzy sets on a universe X was introduced by Zhang [21] in 1994 as a generalization of fuzzy sets. The notion of m -polar fuzzy sets was presented by chen et al. [9] in 2014 as an extension of bipolar fuzzy sets. Bipolar fuzzy sets, m -polar fuzzy (m -PF) sets and several hybrid models of fuzzy sets play a prominent rule in several algebraic structures, such as BCK/BCI -algebras [3, 7, 4, 6, 18, 16, 17], hemirings [11], groups [10] and lie-subalgebras [1, 2]. In 1971, Rosenfeld [19] applied fuzzy sets to groups and proposed the concept of fuzzy subgroups. As a generalization of fuzzy subgroups, Bhakat and Das [8] initiated the notions of $(\epsilon, \epsilon \vee q)$ -fuzzy subgroups by using the concept of fuzzy points and its “belongingness (ϵ)” and “quasi-coincidence (q)” with a fuzzy set. Jun [15] introduced a generalization of fuzzy ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras, called (α, β) -fuzzy ideals. After that, Jana et al. [14] proposed the concept of $(\epsilon, \epsilon \vee q)$ -bipolar fuzzy ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras. Further, Al-Masarwah and Ahmad [5] presented the notion of m -polar $(\epsilon, \epsilon \vee q)$ -fuzzy ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras as a generalization of m -polar fuzzy ideals.

This paper is a continuation of papers [4] and [5]. We introduce the notion of m -polar $(\bar{\epsilon}, \bar{\epsilon} \vee \bar{q})$ fuzzy ideals and investigate some of its properties. We discuss the relation between ordinary ideals and m -polar $(\bar{\epsilon}, \bar{\epsilon} \vee \bar{q})$ fuzzy ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras.

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*Corresponding author.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Some of the significant notions pertaining to BCK/BCI -algebras, m -PF sets, m -PF points and m -PF ideals that are useful for subsequent discussions are stated below. In what follows, let X be a BCK/BCI -algebra unless otherwise specified.

By a BCI -algebra, we mean an algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ satisfying the following axioms for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- (1) $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
- (2) $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- (3) $x * x = 0$,
- (4) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

If a BCI -algebra X satisfies $0 * x = 0 \forall x \in X$, then X is called a BCK -algebra. A partial ordering \leq on a BCK/BCI -algebra X can be defined by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. Any BCK/BCI -algebra X satisfies the following axioms for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- (1) $x * 0 = x$,
- (2) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$.

A non-empty subset J of X is said to be an ideal of X if for all $x, y \in X$:

- (1) $0 \in J$,
- (2) $x * y \in J$ and $y \in J$ imply $x \in J$.

Definition 2.1 ([9]). An m -PF set $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ on $X (\neq \phi)$ is a function $\widehat{\mathcal{H}} : X \rightarrow [0, 1]^m$, where

$$\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) = (p_1 \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), p_2 \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \dots, p_m \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x))$$

is the membership value of every element $x \in X$ and $p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}} : [0, 1]^m \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is the i -th projection mapping for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. The values $\widehat{0} = (0, 0, \dots, 0)$ and $\widehat{1} = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$ are the smallest and largest values in $[0, 1]^m$, respectively.

Definition 2.2 ([4]). An m -PF set $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ of X is said to be an m -PF ideal if the assertions below are valid: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$,
- (2) $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}$.

That is,

- (1) $p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) \geq p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$,
- (2) $p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \inf\{p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}$

for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Definition 2.3 ([4]). Let $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ be an m -PF set of X . Then, the set

$$\widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}} = \{x \in X \mid \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \widehat{t}\}$$

is called the level cut subset of $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ for all $\widehat{t} \in (0, 1]^m$.

An m -PF set $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ of X of the form

$$\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y) = \begin{cases} \widehat{t} = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m) \in (0, 1]^m, & \text{if } y = x \\ \widehat{0} = (0, 0, \dots, 0), & \text{if } y \neq x \end{cases}$$

is called an m -PF point, denoted by $x_{\widehat{t}}$, with support x and value $(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m) = \widehat{t}$.

An m -PF point $x_{\widehat{t}}$

- (1) Belongs to $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$, denoted by $x_{\widehat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$, if $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \widehat{t}$ i.e., $p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq t_i$ for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$,

- (2) Is quasi-coincident with $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$, denoted by $x_{\widehat{t}}q\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$, if $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) + \widehat{t} > \widehat{1}$ i.e., $p_i \circ \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) + t_i > \widehat{1}$ for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

We say that

- (1) $x_{\widehat{t}}\overline{\alpha}\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ if $x_{\widehat{t}}\alpha\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ does not hold,
- (2) $x_{\widehat{t}} \in \vee q\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ if $x_{\widehat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $x_{\widehat{t}}q\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$,
- (3) $x_{\widehat{t}} \in \wedge q\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ if $x_{\widehat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ and $x_{\widehat{t}}q\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$.

Definition 2.4 ([4]). An m -PF set $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ of X is called an m -polar $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy ideal of X if the assertions below are valid: for all $x, y \in X$ and $\widehat{t}, \widehat{s} \in (0, 1]^m$,

- (1) $x_{\widehat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ implies $0_{\widehat{t}} \in \vee q\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$,
- (2) $(x * y)_{\widehat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ and $y_{\widehat{s}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ imply $x_{\inf\{\widehat{t}, \widehat{s}\}} \in \vee q\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$.

3. m -POLAR $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -FUZZY IDEALS

In this section, we define m -polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideals of X and discuss several results.

Definition 3.1. An m -PF set $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ of X is called an m -polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X if the assertions below are valid: for all $x, y \in X$ and $\widehat{t}, \widehat{s} \in (0, 1]^m$,

- (1) $0_{\widehat{t}} \overline{\in} \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ implies $x_{\widehat{t}} \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q}\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$,
- (2) $x_{\inf\{\widehat{t}, \widehat{s}\}} \overline{\in} \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ implies $(x * y)_{\widehat{t}} \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q}\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $y_{\widehat{s}} \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q}\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$.

Example 3.2. Consider a BCK -algebra $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ which is defined in Table 1:

TABLE 1. The operation “ $*$ ”.

$*$	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	0	0
b	b	a	0	0	0
c	c	b	a	0	0
d	d	c	b	a	0

Let $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ be a 3-PF set defined as:

$$\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) = \begin{cases} (0.91, 0.91, 0.97), & \text{if } x = 0 \\ (0.37, 0.37, 0.78), & \text{if } x = a \\ (0.50, 0.50, 0.50), & \text{if } x = b \\ (0.44, 0.44, 0.49), & \text{if } x = c \\ (0.25, 0.25, 0.28), & \text{if } x = d. \end{cases}$$

Clearly, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ is a 3-polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X .

Theorem 3.1. An m -PF set $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ of X is an m -polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X if and only if for all $x, y \in X$:

- (i) $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$,
- (ii) $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}$.

Proof. Let $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ be an m -polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X . Suppose there exists $x \in X$ such that $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{0.5}\} < \widehat{t} = \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$. Then,

$$\hat{t} \in (0.5, 1]^m, 0_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}} \text{ and } x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}.$$

By Definition 3.1 (1), we have $x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$, i.e., $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) < \hat{t}$ or $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) + \hat{t} \leq \widehat{1}$. Since $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) = \hat{t}$, therefore $\hat{t} \leq \widehat{0.5}$. This is a contradiction. Hence, $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Suppose there exist $x, y \in X$ such that $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} < \hat{t} = \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}$. Then,

$$\hat{t} \in (0.5, 1]^m, x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}} \text{ and } (x * y)_{\hat{t}}, y_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}.$$

It follows that $(x * y)_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $y_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$. Then, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y) + \hat{t} \leq \widehat{1}$ or $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y) + \hat{t} \leq \widehat{1}$. Since $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y) \geq \hat{t}$ and $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y) \geq \hat{t}$. It follows that $\hat{t} \leq \widehat{0.5}$, a contradiction. Hence, $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Conversely, let $0_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$. Then, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) < \hat{t}$, either $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$ or $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) < \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$. If $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$, then $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) < \hat{t}$, and so $x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$. That is, $x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$. If $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) < \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$, then by (i), $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \leq \widehat{0.5}$. We consider two cases:

Case (1). If $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) < \hat{t}$, then $x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$, and so $x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$.

Case (2). If $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \hat{t}$, then $\hat{t} \leq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \leq \widehat{0.5}$, it follows that $x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$, and so $x_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$.

Again, let $x_{\inf\{\hat{t}, \hat{s}\}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ for $\hat{t}, \hat{s} \in (0, 1]$. Then, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) < \inf\{\hat{t}, \hat{s}\}$. We consider two cases:

Case (1). If $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \widehat{0.5}$, then

$$\inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\} \leq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) < \inf\{\hat{t}, \hat{s}\}.$$

Consequently, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y) < \hat{t}$ or $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y) < \hat{s}$. That is, $(x * y)_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $y_{\hat{s}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$. Hence, $(x * y)_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $y_{\hat{s}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$.

Case (2). If $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) < \widehat{0.5}$, then

$$\inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\} \leq \widehat{0.5}.$$

Assume $(x * y)_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $y_{\hat{s}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$. Then, $\hat{t} \leq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y) \leq \widehat{0.5}$ or $\hat{s} \leq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y) \leq \widehat{0.5}$. Thus, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y) + \hat{t} \leq \widehat{0.5} + \widehat{0.5} = \widehat{1}$ or $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y) + \hat{s} \leq \widehat{0.5} + \widehat{0.5} = \widehat{1}$. It follows that $(x * y)_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $y_{\hat{s}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ and so $(x * y)_{\hat{t}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ or $y_{\hat{s}} \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}$. Hence, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ is an m -polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X . \square

Theorem 3.2. Any m -polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ of X satisfies: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)$,
- (2) $x * y \leq z \Rightarrow \sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(z)\}$.

Proof. (1) Suppose that $x \leq y$ for all $x, y \in X$. Then, $x * y = 0$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} &\geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\} \\ &= \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\} \\ &\geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y). \end{aligned}$$

(2) Assume that $x * y \leq z$ hold in X . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{0.5}\} &\geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}((x * y) * z), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(z)\} \\ &= \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(z)\} \\ &\geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(z). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ is an m -polar $(\overline{\in}, \overline{\in} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X , we have

$$\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}.$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}, \widehat{0.5}\} &\geq \sup\{\inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}, \widehat{0.5}\} \\ \sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} &\geq \inf\{\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{0.5}\}, \sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y), \widehat{0.5}\}\} \\ &\geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(z), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\} \\ &= \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(z)\}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.3. An m -PF set $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ of X is an m -polar $(\overline{\epsilon}, \overline{\epsilon} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X if and only if $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}} \neq \phi$ is an ideal of X for all $\widehat{t} \in (0.5, 1]^m$.

Proof. Assume that $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ is an m -polar $(\overline{\epsilon}, \overline{\epsilon} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X and $\widehat{t} \in (0.5, 1]^m$. Suppose $x \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$. Then, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \widehat{t}$. Now,

$$\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \widehat{t}.$$

Thus, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) \geq \widehat{t}$. Hence, $0 \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$. Let $x * y, y \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$. Then, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y) \geq \widehat{t}$ and $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y) \geq \widehat{t}$. Now,

$$\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\} \geq \widehat{t}.$$

Thus, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \widehat{t}$, that is, $x \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$. Therefore, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$ is an ideal of X .

Conversely, assume $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}} \neq \phi$ is an ideal of X . Let $x \in X$ be such that $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{0.5}\} < \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$. Choose $\widehat{t} \in (0.5, 1]^m$ such that

$$\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{0.5}\} < \widehat{t} \leq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x).$$

Then, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) < \widehat{t}$ and $x \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$. Since $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$ is an ideal of X , we have $0 \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$, and so $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0) \geq \widehat{t}$, a contradiction. Hence, $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(0), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Assume $x, y \in X$ such that $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} < \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}$. Choose $\widehat{t} \in (0.5, 1]^m$ such that

$$\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} < \widehat{t} \leq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}.$$

Then, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) < \widehat{t}$. Since $x * y, y \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$ and $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$ is an ideal of X , so $x \in \widehat{\mathcal{H}}_{\widehat{t}}$. That is, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x) \geq \widehat{t}$. This is a contradiction. Thus, $\sup\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x), \widehat{0.5}\} \geq \inf\{\widehat{\mathcal{H}}(x * y), \widehat{\mathcal{H}}(y)\}$ for all $x, y \in X$. Hence, $\widehat{\mathcal{H}}$ is an m -polar $(\overline{\epsilon}, \overline{\epsilon} \vee \overline{q})$ -fuzzy ideal of X . □

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, first we have introduced the notion of m -polar $(\overline{\epsilon}, \overline{\epsilon} \vee \overline{q})$ fuzzy ideals and investigated some of its properties. Then, we have discussed the relation between ordinary ideals and m -polar $(\overline{\epsilon}, \overline{\epsilon} \vee \overline{q})$ fuzzy ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Akram and A. Farooq, m -polar fuzzy lie ideals of lie algebras, Quasigroups and Related Systems, 24(2016), 141–150.
- [2] M. Akram, A. Farooq, K. P. Shum. On m -polar fuzzy lie subalgebras, Italian Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, 36(2016), 445–454.
- [3] A. Al-Masarwah, A. G. Ahmad. Doubt bipolar fuzzy subalgebras and ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras, Journal of Mathematical Analysis, 9(2018), 9–27.
- [4] A. Al-Masarwah, A. G. Ahmad. m -polar fuzzy ideals of BCK/BCI -algebras, Journal of King Saud University-Science, (2018), doi:10.1016/j.jksus.2018.10.002.
- [5] A. Al-Masarwah and A. G. Ahmad. m -Polar (α, β) -fuzzy ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras, Symmetry, 11 (2019), 44.

- [6] A. Al-Masarwah, A. G. Ahmad. Novel concepts of doubt bipolar fuzzy H-ideals of BCK/BCI-algebras, *International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control*, 14(2018), 2025–2041.
- [7] A. Al-Masarwah, A. G. Ahmad. On some properties of doubt bipolar fuzzy H-ideals in BCK/BCI-algebras, *European Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 11(2018), 652–670.
- [8] S. K. Bhakat and P. Das. $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -fuzzy subgroups, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 80(1996), 359–368.
- [9] J. Chen, S. Li, S. Ma, X. Wang. m -polar fuzzy sets: An extension of bipolar fuzzy sets, *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014(2014), 416530.
- [10] A. Farooq, G. Alia and M. Akram. On m -polar fuzzy groups, *International Journal of Algebra and Statistic*, 5(2016), 115–127.
- [11] K. Hayat, T. Mahmood, B. Y. Cao. On bipolar anti fuzzy H-ideals in hemirings, *Fuzzy Information and Engineering*, 9(2017), 1–19.
- [12] Y. Imai and K. Iséki. On axiom systems of propositional calculi, *Proceeding of the Japan Academy*, 42(1966), 19–21.
- [13] K. Iséki. An algebra related with a propositional calculus, *Proceeding of the Japan Academy*, 42 (1966), 26–29.
- [14] C. Jana, M. Pal and A. B. Saeid. $(\in, \in \vee q)$ -Bipolar fuzzy BCK/BCI-algebras, *Missouri Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, 29(2017).
- [15] Y. B. Jun. On (α, β) -fuzzy ideals of BCK/BCI-algebras, *Scientiae Mathematicae Japonicae*, 60(2004), 613–617.
- [16] Y. B. Jun, G. Muhiuddin and A. M. Al-roqi. Ideal theory of BCK/BCI -algebras based on double-framed soft sets, *Applied Mathematics and Information Sciences*, 7(2013), 1879–1887.
- [17] Y. B. Jun, G. Muhiuddin, M. A. Ozturk and E. H. Roh. Cubic soft ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras, *Journal of Computational Analysis and Applications*, 22(2017), 929–940.
- [18] Y.B. Jun, S.S. Ahn and G. Muhiuddin. Hesitant fuzzy soft subalgebras and ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras, *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014(2014), Article ID 763929, 7 pages.
- [19] A. Rosenfeld. Fuzzy groups, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, 35(1971), 512–517.
- [20] L. A. Zadeh. Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control*, 8(1965), 338–353.
- [21] W. R. Zhang. Bipolar fuzzy sets and relations: A computational framework for cognitive and modeling and multiagent decision analysis, In *Proceedings of the Fuzzy Information Processing Society Biannual Conference*, San Antonio, TX, USA, 18–21 December 1994; pp. 305–309.

ANAS AL-MASARWAH

SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES, FACULTY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITI KEBANGSAAN MALAYSIA, 43600 UKM BANGI, SELANGOR DE, MALAYSIA

Email address: almasarwah85@gmail.com

ABD GHAFUR AHMAD

SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES, FACULTY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITI KEBANGSAAN MALAYSIA, 43600 UKM BANGI, SELANGOR DE, MALAYSIA

Email address: ghafur@ukm.edu.my